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ABSTRACTS

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Microfluidics aided early detection of Cardiovascular diseases.

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Abstract: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) have become a leading cause of mortality and disability in India and are a serious concern. According to WHO, 17.9 million people's death was recorded from CVDs in 2016, contributing to 31% of deaths globally. Among these figures, 85% were due to heart attack and stroke. Thus, early detection of CVDs are highly desirable.

Lately, exosomes are prominently researched as a diagnostic biomarker for CVDs. Isolation of exosomes from clinical samples is conventionally done using differential ultracentrifugation, ultrafiltration etc. However, these techniques have limitations such as requirement of large equipment's, time consuming and low yield. Hence, a portable, low cost and rapid isolation of exosomes is desirable. In the current study, a microfluidics chip was designed, optimized and simulated using a Comsol Multiphysics software. The chip fabrication will be done by Soft Lithography technique. The fabricated chip will be used to isolate exosomes from the clinical samples of CVDs patients. Furthermore, the isolated exosomes will be detected using carbon dots as a bio-imaging probe. Finally, the exosome-based detection of CVDs will be done on the microfluidic platform.

Keywords: Microfluidics, simulation, exosomes, carbon dots and cardiovascular diseases.

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